

Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin

D7.6 REPORT ON D&C ACTIVITIES VER 2

**WP7 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION,
RRI, PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT**

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¹ PU= Public, SEN=Sensitive

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

CO	Project Coordinator
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
D&C	Dissemination & Communication
GA	Grant Agreement
RRI	Responsible and Innovative Research

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Executive summary

This version 'D7.6 Report on D&C activities Ver. 2' is the second publication of three Dissemination & Communication (D&C) reports devised over the lifespan of the project.

This document reflects an overview of the D&C procedures carried out over the first two years of the project following the strategy described in the AquaWind Dissemination and Communication plan (D7.1). It also reports on the progress of the key performance indicators (KPIs) defined in the same deliverable: D7.1. A final update of the report is expected in M36, at the end of the project.

Introduction

This chapter introduces the scope and aims of the deliverable 'D7.6 Report on D&C activities Ver. 2' developed under WP7.

1.1 AquaWind dissemination and communication work package

The main objective of WP7 is to provide information about the project to a wide audience, including researchers, experts, researchers and technologists, businesses, investors, policy makers and other public and private stakeholders, such as fishermen and citizens. This work package is responsible for carrying out communication activities to improve the visibility of the project itself. WP7 aims to develop tools and frameworks for effective project communication, knowledge and capacity building, peer-to-peer exchange and sharing of results.

This WP will meet all project objectives while sharing and communicating the results of all AquaWind activities to its key stakeholders. The specific objectives of this WP are:

- To make the project visible and increase public awareness of the possibilities of multi-tasking solutions.
- To integrate community adoption to support stakeholder involvement in collaboration with WP1 and to support the creation of a local and European community in support of multi-use solutions.
- To support knowledge transfer, e.g. through scientific and non-scientific publications, academic conferences.
- To join the wide network of EU projects, projects to exchange experiences and promote R&I activities in many applications.
- To strengthen the approach to responsible and innovative research (RRI) and equity.

D&C work in AquaWind aims to ensure the vision of the project, but also enables effective interaction with stakeholders in multi-project relationships. D&C activities are performed through a set of activities defined in the Grant Agreement (GA) project:

Table 1. WP7 tasks' descriptions

Task title	Task description
7.1 Development of the D&C Plan	This task deals with the development and periodic update of the project D&C Plan detailing target groups, communication channels, outputs and providing an initial calendar of D&C activities.
7.2 Creation of D&C products and materials	This task deals with the production of several materials and tools including the project website, logo and corporate image, layout, posters and roll-ups as well as banners for social media, and three videos.
7.3 Organisation of events, webinars, workshops, trainings	This task deals with the organisation of (and attendance to) different events, each of one targeting a specific type of stakeholders.
7.4 Synergies with other funded projects	This task deals with establishing relations with other funded projects to foster synergies in knowledge transfer and in exploitation of AquaWind.
7.5 Monitoring and evaluation of Dissemination and Communication activities	Reporting on D&C activities will be performed to measure efforts and results obtained and modify the D&C plan accordingly.
7.6 Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)	This task foresees the creation of a RRI plan for the project leveraging the MUSICA RRI Self-assessment tool.

1.2 Deliverable scope

The purpose of the D7.5 Report on D&C activities Ver. 2 is to report on the progress of the D&C activities carried out by the AquaWind project during its first two years of life under WP7. **This report summarises the work carried out from the start of the project until the end of the second year (M24).**

This release is the second of three D&C reports to be issued during the project. There are three main chapters with a summary and a conclusion:

Chapter 1 Introduction: *Introduces the scope of the report and presents the general D&C approach set out in the AquaWind D&C project at the beginning of the programme.*

Chapter 2 Update of D&C activities: *shows all D&C activities carried out under WP7 from the start of the project until M24.*

Chapter 3 Indicators' monitoring: *providing an overview of the progress of the project towards the D&C indicators defined in the GA and in the D&C Plan.*

Deliverables are updated throughout the project lifecycle: the latest version of the report will be produced for M36.

1.3 Target groups

As mentioned above, preliminary deliverables and desk research under WP1 and WP7 have defined the main target groups of D&C activities and stakeholder engagement activities. The groups of stakeholders are described below and have been the target of the D&C actions that have been implemented so far and are reported in the present deliverable.

Table 2. Target groups description

Target group	Description
Research community (researchers, PhD students)	Science stakeholders include a diverse network of actors managing, coordinating, or conducting scientific research related to marine activities. This group includes the research community, science managers as well students and PhD scientists. The science category includes actors at local, national, intergovernmental, and European levels as well as representatives of other EU projects.
Industry Representatives, Investors	This category includes representatives of the fishery sector, aquaculture, renewable energy but also maritime transport. In particular companies willing to commercialise the products and services developed in the demo work packages will require robust exploitation plans, risk and benefit assessments, which will be produced under WP5. They will also benefit from the networking opportunities and communication activities offered under WP7.
Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations)	This category includes both citizens and organisations that operate in the marine field and are affected by marine related activities and citizens who have no specific knowledge of multi-use projects and are not affected by marine activities in their everyday life.

Fisheries communities	The fisheries communities are part of the societal actors but are also a key target group on its own. Due to the nature of the project, combining not only offshore wind energy that might interfere with fisheries space and the fishes itself but with the aquaculture part might pose a threat to the artisanal ways of fishing in the islands. For this reason, many activities for WP1, task 1.3 and task 1.4 consider this target group in specific.
Policy and decision-makers	This group will require short and concise recommendations and visual documentation facilitating the understanding of how marine multi-use projects can impact a broader policy sector and how policy can support or hamper their implementation. Policymakers at regional, national and EU level will be targeted.

Following the definition of the key project target groups, core D&C channels and type of information to be shared with each stakeholder group has been defined in D7.1. The D&C activities reported in this deliverable have been carried out following this approach.

Table 3. Target groups communication details

Target group	Communication channels	Type of information
Research community (researchers, PhD students)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project results 	
Industry Representatives, Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business/exploitation plan 	
Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations) + Fisheries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project impact assessment 	
Policy and decision-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advantages of the prototype 	

2. Update on dissemination & communication activities

This chapter reports on the D&C activities implemented throughout the first two project year in line with the D&C Plan and the GA.

2.1 Visual identity and information materials

AquaWind has developed a dedicated visual identity for an efficient dissemination of the results of the project. The first and central element to develop in order to have a consistent visual identity is the logo and the main colours and style that have been used – and will continue to be used - in D&C materials and all other documents of the project, thus defining the project’s identity and ensuring recognisability.

The logo in Figure 3 was developed by the WP leader CE with the feedback and suggestions of all partners. To develop the logo, the two main elements of the multi-use solution: Aquaculture and Off-shore wind energy were given special importance being represented by the windmills and the fish. Another element of special importance is the Circular economy which is represented by the circle closing the design.

Figure 1. AquaWind's logotype

Figure 2. AquaWind's colours and typography

Código HEX	
#00a4a8	#004f7d
#3dc0e8	#edb400

Main typography

Myriad Pro Regular AaBbCcDdEeFfGg
 Myriad Pro Condensed AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKk
 Myriad Pro Condensed Italic AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJj
 Myriad Pro Light AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLl
 Myriad Pro Semibold AaBbCcDdEe
 Myriad Pro Semibold Italic AaBbCcDdEeFfGg
 Myriad Pro Bold Condensed AaBbCcDdEeFfGg
 Myriad Pro Bold AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLl
 Myriad Pro Bold Italic AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLl
 Myriad Pro Bold Condensed Italic AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLl

Secondary typography

Calibri
 Designer: Luc(as) De Groot
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890~!@#%&^*(){}[]'""?
 The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog.
 The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog.
 The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog.

Following the developed visual identity, initial information and promotional materials have been developed. These include:

 Leaflet and poster.

The AquaWind project created a comprehensive leaflet during its initial months, which encompasses essential information about the project. In addition, the leaflet has been designed to adapt to various attended events, ensuring that the content is tailored to effectively reach the project's specific target groups. General information about the project has been incorporated into the leaflet, ensuring that it serves as a valuable resource for disseminating key project details and engaging with stakeholders across different events about its prototyping and offshore renewable energy combined with aquaculture.

Figure 3. First draft of AquaWind’s Leaflet/Poster

In line with the project’s goals an update of the project’s visual identity was created to resonate with key stakeholders. To represent this, a concept of minimalism has been applied to all the promotional materials enhancing its quality and reproduction in any type of formats. This update reflects WP7 dedication to innovation and constant change without regard for past patterns, always aiming to fit in well with the current communication’s trends.

Below, WP7 presents the **updated leaflet**, which has now been converted into a tri-fold brochure. In this new version, the project has renewed the images of the wind energy and aquaculture prototypes.

Figure 4. AquaWind’s Leaflet/Poster new version

 Roll-up

A designed roll-up banner measuring 85cm x 200cm has been developed for AquaWind. This promotional material has been strategically distributed to partners for use during various D&C activities. In particular, the roll-up banner has been prominently displayed at different events, helping to raise awareness and generate interest among attendees.

Figure 5. AquaWind's Roll-up

From the above version, **a new roll-up was created**. This version contains images of the wind energy and aquaculture prototype progress, maintaining a coherent branding in line with the updated project's visual identity.

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Figure 6. AquaWind's Roll-up new version

Other templates

In addition, templates for banners, project documents, deliverables and Power Point presentations have been developed following the established visual identity.

Figure 7. AquaWind’s corporate templates

Among the updates to the project’s promotional material is also the PowerPoint template, which has been redesigned with a more minimalist approach. This new design allows to create cleaner, tidier and more engaging presentations for the audience at our events. With these changes, the project aimed to improve the clarity and visual impact of the presentations, ensuring that communication is more effective and professional.

Figure 8. AquaWind’s corporate templates new version

2.2 Website

The **AquaWind website** (<https://aquawind.eu/>) is a dynamic platform that undergoes continuous updates and enhancements to engage a broad audience of international and EU stakeholders. Serving as a comprehensive window, the website showcases various digital elements, news, and events associated with the project, establishing itself as a

primary tool for effectively communicating not just the message, but also the purpose of AquaWind to the public. The initial version of the website was created during the project's early stages, as documented in D7.1 of the Dissemination and Communication Plan submitted in M3. Since then, consistent efforts have been made to improve the website's design, structure, and activity tracking. As a result, it has evolved significantly, aligning with the evolving needs of its users, i.e., to increase accessibility and reading, the website has experimented adjustments to its design.

The sitemap has been updated to increase indexability and new events, previews, news and results have been added. A Google Analytics tag has been inserted on the website to measure visits under Global site tag: UA-254230170-1 (gtag.js).

The Cookies Policy has been put to the footer section in a prominent location. The website displays a pop-up window informing and requesting consent from visitors regarding their General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance options.

As an ever-evolving platform, this document will be regularly updated to accommodate the ongoing progress of the project and to address emerging needs and information that require sharing and dissemination.

Below, a preview of its refreshed design can be found.

Figure 9. Website's preview

Joining Forces for a Greener Future

At AquaWind, we believe that collaboration is key to achieving a more sustainable future. To reach this goal, we invite you to join the AquaWind community and share your expertise, insights, and best practices with us. Together, we can make a difference in the aquaculture industry.

One of the key goals of AquaWind is to achieve an inclusive industry that allows the efforts of a multidisciplinary stakeholder consortium in the Atlantic basin, including the UK, Ireland, and other regional partners, to lead the way in sustainable aquaculture production.

Website insights

The following insights show the overall data in terms of statistics and interactions with the project’s website since its launch at the earliest stage of the project²:

² Data analytics as of 23rd August 2023.

Figure 10. Cumulative website's analytics (2022-2024)

Overall, since its start, the project recorded over **9.200 visits** to its website. Most of these visits come from Google searches, although it also received traffic through the official CINEA website, as well as from LinkedIn and the project's newsletter.

 Visitor countries

Figure 11. World's ranking of visitors

Analysis of the top visitor countries reveal that AquaWind predominantly garners visits from Spanish and French audience since the website's launch, followed by Belgium, China, and The Netherlands.

Website articles

The AquaWind project has made every effort to inform and involve stakeholders by publishing several articles on its website.

The aim of these articles is to provide up-to-date news and updates related to the project or the European Commission, as well as to inform about upcoming events in which AquaWind is involved. For easier access, a table with a list of articles and related links is shown below. This comprehensive approach ensures that stakeholders are fully informed and can easily access the information they are looking for.

Table 4 below presents a list of articles written by the WP7 leader and published on the website. In addition, Table 5 presents articles on AquaWind published by the project partners on their own websites.

Table 4. List of AquaWind's website articles

	Date	Title	Link
Year 1 (M1-12)	14/10/2022	Gran Canaria leads the pioneering AquaWind project to merge wind power and aquaculture	https://aquawind.eu/2022/10/14/gran-canaria-leads-the-pioneering-aquawind-project-to-merge-wind-power-and-aquaculture/
	28/10/2022	Offshore wind power and fishing sector conference in the Canary Islands	https://aquawind.eu/2022/10/28/offshore-wind-power-and-fishing-sector-conference-in-the-canary-islands/
	18/11/2022	The AquaWind project will be present at the XVIII Spanish National Congress of Aquaculture	https://aquawind.eu/2022/11/18/the-aquawind-project-will-be-present-at-the-xviii-spanish-national-congress-of-aquaculture/
	24/11/2022	AquaWind surprises at the Cádiz National Aquaculture Congress	https://aquawind.eu/2022/11/24/aquawind-surprises-at-the-cadiz-national-aquaculture-congress/
	13/12/2022	Spain will receive €1.12 billion from the EMFAF 2021-2027	https://aquawind.eu/2022/12/13/spain-will-receive-e1-12-billion-from-the-emfaf-2021-2027/
	21/02/2023	Latest EU policy measures for more sustainable fisheries,	https://aquawind.eu/2023/02/21/latest-eu-policy-measures-for-more-sustainable-fisheries-aquaculture-and-marine-ecosystems/

	aquaculture and marine ecosystems		
28/03/2023	AquaFuture Spain receives the AquaWind project during its first day	https://aquawind.eu/2023/03/28/aquafuture-spain-receives-the-aquawind-project-during-its-first-day/	
28/04/2023	European Maritime Day 2023	https://aquawind.eu/2023/04/28/european-maritime-day-2023/	
24/05/2024	An historic achievement: Treaty of the High Seas is adopted	https://aquawind.eu/2023/05/24/an-historic-achievement-treaty-of-the-high-seas-is-adopted/	
31/05/2023	The EU Blue Economy Report 2023	https://aquawind.eu/2023/05/30/the-eu-blue-economy-report-2023/	
1/06/23	AquaWind meets its sister project FLORA	https://aquawind.eu/2023/06/01/aquawind-meets-its-sister-project-flora/	
28/06/2023	First public results of AquaWind	https://aquawind.eu/2023/06/28/first-public-results-of-aquawind/	
13/07/2023	AquaWind at FIMAR 2023	https://aquawind.eu/2023/07/13/aquawind-at-fimar-2023/	
2/08/2023	Sustainable fishing in the EU: state of play and orientations for 2024	https://aquawind.eu/2023/08/02/sustainable-fishing-in-the-eu-state-of-play-and-orientations-for-2024/	
8/08/2023	EC Launches Consultation for Energy Transition Partnership in EU Fisheries and Aquaculture Sector	https://aquawind.eu/2023/08/08/ec-launches-consultation-for-energy-transition-partnership-in-eu-fisheries-and-aquaculture-sector/	
16/08/2023	EU's Progress Towards UN Sustainable Development Goals: A Mixed Bag for "Life Below Water"	https://aquawind.eu/2023/08/16/eus-progress-towards-un-sustainable-development-goals-a-mixed-bag-for-life-below-water/	
23/08/2023	Commissioner Sinkevičius Calls for Action to Improve Baltic Sea Environment	https://aquawind.eu/2023/08/23/commissioner-sinkevicius-calls-for-action-to-improve-baltic-sea-environment/	
Year 2 (M13-24)	30/08/2023	United and ultfarms Joint Webinar	https://aquawind.eu/2023/08/30/united-and-ultfarms-joint-webinar/
	12/09/2023	Exploring Breakthroughs: Progress on the Multi-use Platform	https://aquawind.eu/2023/09/12/exploring-breakthroughs-progress-on-the-multi-use-platform/

15/09/2023	AquaWind featured on EU CINEA newsletter	https://aquawind.eu/2023/09/15/aquawind-featured-on-eu-cinea-newsletter/
22/09/2023	Navalia Meeting 2023: Setting Sail Towards Innovation and Collaboration	https://aquawind.eu/2023/09/22/navalia-meeting-2023-setting-sail-towards-innovation-and-collaboration/
5/10/2023	2023 Barometer of Blue Economy Activity in the Canary Islands by Cetecima	https://aquawind.eu/2023/10/05/2023-barometer-of-blue-economy-activity-in-the-canary-islands-by-cetecima/
24/10/2023	AquaWind stakeholder survey launched!	https://aquawind.eu/2023/10/24/aquawind-stakeholder-survey-launched/
15/11/2023	AquaWind at Offshore Wind Congress, Strengthening Spain's Technological Hub	https://aquawind.eu/2023/11/15/aquawind-at-offshore-wind-congress-strengthening-spains-technological-hub/
30/11/2023	AquaWind Project's Engaging Participation in World Aquaculture Day Professional sessions	https://aquawind.eu/2023/11/30/aquawind-projects-engaging-participation-in-world-aquaculture-day-professional-sessions/
5/12/2023	Recently our project teams from ULPGC, ACIISI-GOBCAN, and ENEROCEAN met at the Las Palmas harbour for a technical inspection of the W2Power prototype	https://aquawind.eu/2023/12/05/recently-our-project-teams-from-ulpgc-aciisi-gobcan-and-enerocean-met-at-the-las-palmas-harbour-for-a-technical-inspection-of-the-w2power-prototype/
18/12/2023	AquaWind Project Showcases Innovations at Canarian Blue Economy Event	https://aquawind.eu/2023/12/18/aquawind-project-showcases-innovations-at-canarian-blue-economy-event/
9/01/2024	WindEurope's Annual Event 2024 is Set to Ignite Bilbao with Insights, Innovation, and Unrivalled Networking	https://aquawind.eu/2024/01/09/windeuropes-annual-event-2024-is-set-to-ignite-bilbao-with-insights-innovation-and-unrivalled-networking/
15/01/2024	Aquaculture prototype updates: ULPGC is working on the set-up of cooper alloy nets for the aquaculture cage.	https://aquawind.eu/2024/01/15/revolutionising-aquaculture-ulpgc-introduces-innovative-metal-alloy-nets-with-plocan-ceo-collaboration/
22/01/2024	Energy Transition Partnership	https://aquawind.eu/2024/01/22/energy-transition-partnership/
29/01/2024	Last Chance! Survey Extended Until 29 th February	https://aquawind.eu/2024/01/29/extending-exploration-aquawind-project-lengthens-survey-period-by-one-month-to-enhance-stakeholder-engagement-and-insight-gathering/

1/02/2024	Strategic Distribution of Venture Capital in Global Aquaculture	https://aquawind.eu/2024/02/01/strategic-distribution-of-venture-capital-in-global-aquaculture/
2/02/2024	Successful Technology Breakfast in Fuerteventura: Boosting Development through the RIS3 Strategy	https://aquawind.eu/2024/02/02/successful-technology-breakfast-in-fuerteventura-boosting-development-through-the-ris3-strategy/
5/02/2024	Aquaculture Innovations: Ten Aquaculture Startups Join the Inaugural Bright Tides Regenerative Agriculture Accelerator	https://aquawind.eu/2024/02/05/aquaculture-innovations-ten-aquaculture-startups-join-the-inaugural-bright-tides-regenerative-agriculture-accelerator/
23/02/2024	AquaWind Project Among Diverse Initiatives Showcased at European Oceans Days	https://aquawind.eu/2024/02/23/aquawind-project-among-diverse-initiatives-showcased-at-european-ocean-days/
28/02/2024	The first half of the AquaWind Project was successfully completed	https://aquawind.eu/2024/02/28/the-first-half-of-the-aquawind-project-was-successfully-completed/
1/03/2024	New developments: we have already installed the aquaculture cage in water	https://aquawind.eu/2024/03/01/new-developments-we-have-already-installed-the-aquaculture-cage-in-water/
11/03/2024	At the European Ocean Days, AquaWind presents a visionary approach to integrating aquaculture and renewable energy	https://aquawind.eu/2024/03/11/at-the-european-ocean-days-aquawind-presents-a-visionary-approach-to-integrating-aquaculture-and-renewable-energy/
14/03/2024	AquaWind: Progress and collaboration at the Mid-Project Meeting	https://aquawind.eu/2024/03/14/aquawind-progress-and-collaboration-at-the-mid-project-meeting/
21/03/2024	BEST students visit the Taliarte dock facilities to explore the AquaWind project	https://aquawind.eu/2024/03/21/best-students-visit-the-taliarte-dock-facilities-to-explore-the-aquawind-project/
1/04/2024	AquaWind at WindEurope 2024	https://aquawind.eu/2024/04/01/aquawind-at-windeurope-2024/
16/04/2024	Brussels becomes the global epicenter of the circular economy this week!	https://aquawind.eu/2024/04/16/brussels-becomes-the-global-epicentre-of-the-circular-economy-this-week/
19/04/2024	The 2024 Hannover Messe is well underway!	https://aquawind.eu/2024/04/19/the-2024-hannover-messe-is-well-underway/

2/05/2024	European Commission recommendations to encourage the development of aquaculture in the European Union	https://aquawind.eu/2024/05/02/european-commission-recommendations-to-encourage-the-development-of-aquaculture-in-the-european-union/
13/05/2024	AquaWind joins the Canary Islands Science and Innovation Ministries 2024	https://aquawind.eu/2024/05/13/aquawind-joins-the-ministerios-de-ciencia-y-innovacion-de-canarias-en-2024/
15/05/2024	The European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund celebrates a decade of supporting sustainability and innovation	https://aquawind.eu/2024/05/15/the-european-maritime-fisheries-and-aquaculture-fund-celebrates-a-decade-of-supporting-sustainability-and-innovation/
20/05/2024	AquaWind consortium partners prepare for safe and healthy operations in pilot demonstrator	https://aquawind.eu/2024/05/20/aquawind-consortium-partners-prepare-for-safe-and-healthy-operations-in-pilot-demonstrator/
22/05/2024	AquaWind project organizes a webinar on Multipurpose Ocean Platform Demonstrator Pilots	https://aquawind.eu/2024/05/22/the-aquawind-project-organises-a-webinar-on-multipurpose-ocean-platform-demonstrator-pilots/
24/05/2024	AquaWind will participate in the XIX National Aquaculture Congress (XIX-CNA)	https://aquawind.eu/2024/05/24/aquawind-will-participate-in-the-xix-national-aquaculture-congress-xix-cna/
28/05/2024	AquaWind will be present at Fimar 2024	https://aquawind.eu/2024/05/28/aquawind-will-be-present-at-fimar-2024/
11/06/2024	AquaWind Drives the Blue Economy at FIMAR 2024	https://aquawind.eu/2024/05/28/aquawind-will-be-present-at-fimar-2024/
19/06/2024	Technological Breakfast in El Hierro on 14 June 2024: Socioeconomic Potential through the RIS3 Strategy	https://aquawind.eu/2024/06/19/technological-breakfast-in-el-hierro-on-14-june-2024-socioeconomic-potential-through-the-ris3-strategy/
20/06/2024	AquaWind at the XIX National Congress of Aquaculture	https://aquawind.eu/2024/06/20/aquawind-at-the-xix-national-congress-of-aquaculture/
21/06/2024	Successful webinar FLORA and AquaWind on June 20th	https://aquawind.eu/2024/06/21/successful-webinar-flora-and-aquawind-on-june-20th/
25/06/2024	Presentation of the AquaWind Project in Rome	https://aquawind.eu/2024/06/25/presentation-of-the-aquawind-project-in-rome/

18/07/2024	Innovation and Sustainability Drive Growth in the EU Blue Economy	https://aquawind.eu/2024/07/18/innovation-and-sustainability-drive-growth-in-the-eu-blue-economy/
26/07/2024	Technology Breakfast in La Gomera on 24 July 2024: Development Opportunities through the RIS3 Strategy	https://aquawind.eu/2024/07/26/technology-breakfast-in-la-gomera-on-24-july-2024-development-opportunities-through-the-ris3-strategy/

Table 5. List of AquaWind articles published on project partners' websites

	Date	Partner	Title	Link
Year 1 (M1-12)	7/10/2022	ULPGC	ARRANCA EL PROYECTO EUROPEO AQUAWIND	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/en/noticias/item/703-arranca-el-proyecto-europeo-aquawind.html
	10/10/2022	CMC	KICK OFF Meeting Proyecto AquaWind	https://www.clustermc.es/kick-off-meeting-proyecto-aquawind/
	11/10/2022	PLOCAN	Lanzamiento del proyecto europeo AquaWind de energía eólica y acuicultura offshore que coordina la ACIISI	https://www.plocan.eu/lanzamiento-del-proyecto-europeo-aquawind-de-energia-eolica-y-acuicultura-offshore-que-coordina-la-aciisi/
	11/10/2022	CE	Gran Canaria leads the pioneering AquaWind project to merge wind power and aquaculture	https://consulta-europa.com/gran-canaria-leads-the-pioneering-aquawind-project-to-merge-wind-power-and-aquaculture/
	14/10/2022	CMC	Encuentro de la eólica marina con el sector pesquero en Canarias	https://www.clustermc.es/encuentro-de-la-eolica-marina-con-el-sector-pesquero-en-canarias/
	25/10/2022	ULPGC	La Vicerrectora de Investigación Marisol Izquierdo acude a la Jornada de Energía Eólica Marina	https://www.ulpgc.es/noticia/2022/10/25/vicerrectora-investigacion-marisol-izquierdo-acude-jornada-energia-eolica-marina
	27/10/2022	CMC	La eólica marina y el sector pesquero apuestan por la convivencia	https://www.clustermc.es/la-eolica-marina-offshore-y-el-sector-pesquero-apuestan-por-la-convivencia/

28/10/2022	CMC	Canarias lidera el proyecto AquaWind para fusionar energía eólica y acuicultura	https://www.clustermc.es/canarias-lidera-el-proyecto-aquawind-para-fusionar-energia-eolica-y-acuicultura/
24/11/2022	ULPGC - FPCT, CMC	AquaWind sorprende en el Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura de Cádiz	https://www.ecoaqua.eu/es/blog/aquawind-sorprende-en-el-congreso-nacional-de-acuicultura-de-cadiz-a3542.html ; https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/es/noticias/item/717-aquawind-sorprende-en-el-congreso-nacional-de-acuicultura-de-cadiz.html ; https://www.clustermc.es/aquawind-sorprende-en-el-congreso-nacional-de-acuicultura-de-cadiz/
25/11/2022	ULPGC	Presentado el proyecto AquaWind en el Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura de Cádiz	https://www.ulpgc.es/noticia/2022/11/25/presentado-proyecto-aquawind-congreso-nacional-acuicultura-cadiz
25/11/2022	CE	AquaWind surprises at the Cádiz National Aquaculture Congress	https://consulta-europa.com/aquawind-surprises-at-the-cadiz-national-aquaculture-congress/
31/03/2023	CMC	El Proyecto AquaWind presente en Aquafuture Spain	https://www.clustermc.es/el-proyecto-aquawind-presente-en-aquafuture-spain/
31/03/2023	CE	Consulta Europa attends AquaFuture Spain event with AquaWind project	https://consulta-europa.com/consulta-europa-attends-aquafuture-spain-event-with-aquawind-project/
01/06/2023	PLOCAN	Collaboration of the European projects AquaWind and FLORA that will be tested in PLOCAN	https://plocan.eu/en/collaboration-of-the-european-projects-aquawind-and-flora-that-will-be-tested-in-plocan
01/06/2023	ULPGC	PROYECTOS EUROPEOS AQUAWIND Y FLORA EXPLORAN SINERGIAS EN EVENTO CONJUNTO EN GRAN CANARIA	https://www.fpct.ulpgc.es/en/noticias/item/780-proyectos-europeos-aquawind-y-flora-exploran-sinerrias-en-evento-conjunto-en-gran-canaria.html

	02/06/2023	CE	AquaWind project explores synergies with FLORA in a joint event in Gran Canaria	https://consulta-europa.com/aquawind-project-explores-synergies-in-a-joint-event-in-gran-canaria/
	08/06/2023	CMC	Los proyectos europeos AquaWind y FLORA exploran sinergias en evento conjunto en Gran Canaria	https://www.clustermc.es/los-proyectos-europeos-aquawind-y-flora-exploran-sinergias-en-evento-conjunto-en-gran-canaria/
	19/06/2023	CMC	CMC y FEDEPORT dan a conocer las profesiones azules en FIMAR 2023	https://www.clustermc.es/cmc-y-fedeport-dan-a-conocer-las-profesiones-azules-en-fimar-2023/
	03/07/2023	CE	First public results of AquaWind project	https://consulta-europa.com/first-public-results-of-aquawind-project/
Year 2 (M13-24)	09/2023	GOBCAN-ACIISI	AquaWind project	https://www.gobiernodecanarias.org/conocimiento/temas/investigacion/proyectosh2020/
	09/2023	WavEC	AquaWind project	https://www.wavec.org/en/research-development/projects/aquawind
	17/10/2023	CMC	2º Boletín del proyecto AquaWind	https://mailchi.mp/clustermc/noticias-de-inter-17073236?e=[UNIQID]
	13/12/2023	GOBCAN-ACIISI	Canarias avanza en su estrategia de especialización inteligente	https://www3.gobiernodecanarias.org/noticias/canarias-avanza-en-su-estrategia-de-especializacion-inteligente/
	26/02/2024	CMC	¡Últimos días! Participa en la encuesta del proyecto AquaWind	https://www.clustermc.es/ultimos-dias-participa-en-la-encuesta-del-proyecto-aquawind/
	08/03/2024	ULPGC	Proyecto AquaWind: Recently our project teams from ULPGC, ACIISI - GOBCAN, and ENEROCEAN met at the Las Palmas harbour for a	https://otc.ulpgc.es/proyecto-aquawind-recently-our-project-teams-from-ulpgc-aciisi-gobcan-and-enerocean-met-at-the-las-

		technical inspection of the W2Power prototype	palmas-harbour-for-a-technical-inspection-of-the-w2power-prototype/
13/03/2024	GOBCAN-ACIISI	La primera plataforma multiuso de eólica flotante y acuicultura ya está lista para su botadura	https://www3.gobiernodecanarias.org/noticias/la-primer-plataforma-multiuso-de-eolica-flotante-y-acuicultura-ya-esta-lista-para-su-botadura/
13/03/2024	CMC	La plataforma multiuso de eólica flotante y acuicultura del proyecto AquaWind ya está preparada para su botadura	https://www.clustermc.es/el-cluster-maritimo-de-canarias-en-su-compromiso-con-la-innovacion-y-la-seguridad-del-sector-te-ofrece-el-curso-computacion-y-seguridad-en-la-nube-2/
14/03/2024	CE	La primera plataforma polivalente para energía eólica marina flotante y acuicultura de la cuenca atlántica está lista para su lanzamiento	https://consulta-europa.com/es/la-primer-plataforma-polivalente-para-energia-eolica-marina-flotante-y-acuicultura-de-la-cuenca-atlantica-esta-lista-para-su-lanzamiento/
15/03/2024	PLOCAN	AquaWind: Progreso y Colaboración en la reunión anual de proyecto	https://plocan.eu/aquawind-progreso-y-colaboracion-en-la-reunion-anual-de-proyecto
20/03/2024	GOBCAN-ACIISI	Estudiantes de carreras tecnológicas conocen de primera mano el proyecto AquaWind coordinado por ACIISI	https://www3.gobiernodecanarias.org/noticias/estudiantes-de-carreras-tecnologicas-conocen-de-primer-mano-el-proyecto-aquawind-coordinado-por-aciisi/
26/03/2024	CMC	El CMC destaca el potencial de Canarias para la eólica marina en WindEurope 2024	https://www.clustermc.es/el-cmc-destaca-el-potencial-de-canarias-para-la-eolica-marina-en-windeurope-2024/

10/05/2024	GOBCAN-ACISI	Estudiantes y familias viajan con las Miniferias a los ecosistemas marinos de Canarias	https://www3.gobiernodecanarias.org/noticias/estudiantes-y-familias-viajan-con-las-miniferias-a-los-ecosistemas-marinos-de-canarias/
03/06/2024	CMC	El CMC participa en el European Maritime Day de Svendborg, Dinamarca	https://www.clustermc.es/el-cmc-involucrado-en-el-european-maritime-day/
19/06/2024	CMC	AquaWind presente en el XIX Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura	AquaWind presente en el XIX Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura – Cluster Marino Marítimo de Canarias (clustermc.es)

Last but not least, it can be highlighted that the AquaWind project has been featured on the CINEA website:

Table 6. AquaWind articles published on CINEA website.

Date	Title	Link
11/07/2023	AQUAWIND - Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/featured-projects/aquawind-innovative-multi-use-prototype-combining-offshore-renewable-energy-and-aquaculture-atlantic_en
24/07/2023	Promoting the sustainable blue economy: EMFAF Flagship call 2021 projects – a year on	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/promoting-sustainable-blue-economy-emfaf-flagship-call-2021-projects-year-2023-07-24_en
27/07/2024	AquaWind project - Offshore platform to produce electricity and food	https://blue-economy-observatory.ec.europa.eu/news/aquawind-project-offshore-platform-produce-electricity-and-food-2023-07-27_en

2.3 Social media

For communication purposes a set of social media accounts has been established, each targeting different audiences. These accounts are regularly updated providing valuable

information on project results, partner updates, organised events, interviews, and other relevant project-related activities. The social media channels serve as dynamic platforms for sharing up-to-date information, engaging with stakeholders, and promoting awareness about the project. The AquaWind project ensures widespread communication of project updates and facilitates active participation and interaction with interested individuals and organisations.

The following table shows a general view about the performance on each channel from October 2022 (M2) until August 2024 (M24):

Table 7. Social media channels

Channels	Link	Nº posts	Followers	Nº posts	Followers
	AquaWind Project https://www.linkedin.com/in/aquawind-project-9b321b247/	52	272	132	937
	@aquawindproject https://www.instagram.com/aquawindproject/	23	462	76	562
	AquaWind Project https://www.facebook.com/aquawind.eu	49	80	119	113
	@AquawindP https://twitter.com/AquawindP	62	135	160	237
		Year 1 (M2-12)		Year 2 (M13-24)	

Social Media Insights

LinkedIn

The LinkedIn account has demonstrated excellent content performance in the first year of the project, garnering a **remarkable 16,107 impressions**. This high number of impressions showcased the effectiveness of AquaWind's content strategy in capturing attention, generating interest and fostering meaningful engagement with the project's

target audience. Through its LinkedIn presence, AquaWind has been able to establish an initial strong digital footprint, starting to cultivate valuable connections within the industry and the research community.

Figure 12. Content performance – Year 1

In the second year of the project, a further significant increase in the number of impressions was attained, **reaching a total of 61,992**. This increase reflects the success of AquaWind's content strategy, which is designed to attract audience attention, generate interest and encourage real engagement with our target audience. The number of impressions gained demonstrates how our communication strategies have impacted users, ensuring that our message is seen by a wide range of people and increasing the impact of the project in the communities we aim to reach.

Figure 13. Content performance – Year 2

 Facebook

In Year 1, Aquawind's Facebook account experienced good engagement with a following of 80 individuals and a reach of over **13,700 impressions**. This demonstrated the growing interest and visibility of the project among Facebook users. The account has effectively utilised this platform to disseminate project updates, share relevant content, and engage with stakeholders and the wider online community.

Figure 14. Facebook Growth – Year 1

During the second year, AquaWind's Facebook account has progressively grown, reaching a total of 116 followers and more than **5,700 impressions** compared to last year, achieving **over 20,200 impressions in total since the beginning of the project**.

Figure 15. Facebook Performance – Year 2

Performance

Instagram

The AquaWind project also maintained an active presence on Instagram, where its official account reached 6,000 impressions in the first year. Through engaging content and regular updates, AquaWind has used Instagram effectively to communicate and disseminate the project.

Figure 16. Instagram Growth - Year 1

While in the **second year of the project**, the official account has attained a total of over **2,000 impressions**.

Figure 17. Instagram Growth - Year 2

Twitter/X

AquaWind's Twitter/X account has been actively engaging with its audience over the first year, garnering increasing traction and interaction and attaining 153 followers likes and 31 retweets from a total of 62 tweets.

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Figure 18. Twitter Interactions – Year 1

During the second year of the project, AquaWind's Twitter/X account has continued to demonstrate active interaction with its audience, leading to a gradual increase in followers (213) and engagement. During this time, it has accumulated **6.500 impressions**.

Figure 19. Twitter Interactions – Year 2

2.4 Newsletter

To ensure effective dissemination of project updates and achievements, the AquaWind newsletter serves as a valuable communication tool. It provides regular updates on project activities, highlights latest developments, and promotes awareness of the project and its advancements.

The **first newsletter was released in February 2023 and distributed to 108 recipients**. This tool plays an important role generating interest and engagement among stakeholders promoting the vision of integrating marine renewable energy production and finfish aquaculture in the Atlantic region.

Figure 20. First newsletter release

Moreover, the second project newsletter was published in September 2023 and delivered to 155 recipients. This newsletter included important updates on the project's progress and relevant information for our audience. Thanks to its effective distribution, stakeholders were able to keep abreast of recent changes and improve communication with our partners and stakeholders.

Figure 21. Second newsletter release

Subsequently, the **third newsletter** was launched in **March 2024**. Continuing the strategy of keeping its audience informed about project developments and activities, this edition was distributed to **183 recipients**. To keep all stakeholders updated and committed to the project's objectives, the newsletter provided a detailed description of recent achievements and next steps.

Figure 22. Second newsletter release

WP7 is currently working on the fourth newsletter, which will be published in autumn 2024, upon the placement of the AquaWind combined, multi-use prototype on waters at the test site. This next newsletter will provide up-to-date and relevant information, reflecting the most recent developments and the initiation of the pilot demonstration phase, as well as highlighting future initiatives of the project.

The newsletters design was developed according to the visual identity, and it is written and available in English for download from the AquaWind [website](#).

Continuous efforts are made to promote newsletter's subscriptions via the website, the social media, and when organising events and other stakeholder engagement activities. **To date, the project has reached 242 newsletter subscribers.**

2.5 Press releases

Project partners have already made significant progress in the development of press releases by showcasing AquaWind to a wider audience and creating greater awareness of the project and its goals. With a total of **62 press releases generated thus far**, they have emerged as a vital component for increasing visibility and engagement.

To date, there have been **30 national press releases**, aimed at disseminating project updates and achievements within partners countries. Additionally, the project has reached a broader audience with **5 international press releases**, highlighting its global significance and impact. Moreover, the project's regional impact is emphasised through **27 national/regional press releases**, including **3 radio** appearances and **1 publication in a prominent paper magazine**, targeting specific geographical areas to raise awareness and foster local engagement.

Table 8. Press release list

	Date	Title	Media	Type of media	Dissemination level	Link
	Project launch & kick off meeting					
Year 1 (M1 – 12)	1/07/2022	EMFAF flagship projects on regional maritime cooperation kick off	CINEA	ONLINE PRESS	International	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/emfaf-flagship-projects-regional-maritime-cooperation-kick-2022-07-01_en
	6/07/2022	7 PROYECTOS DEL FEMPA PARA LA COOPERACIÓN MARÍTIMA	Sector Marítimo	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://sectormaritimo.es/7-proyectos-del-fempa-para-la-cooperacion-maritima
	8/07/2022	Seven EU funded projects are kicking off to strengthen sea basin-level collaboration in the Atlantic, the Black Sea and the Western Mediterranean.	European office of cyprus	ONLINE PRESS	International	https://eoc.org.cy/emfaf-flagship-projects-on-regional-maritime-cooperation-kick-off/
	11/10/2022	Arranca el proyecto europeo AquaWind, que une la energía eólica offshore con la acuicultura	IPAC	ONLINE PRESS	National	http://www.ipacuicultura.com/noticias/en_portada/82206/arranca_el_proyecto_europeo_aquawind_que_une_la_energia_eolica_offshore_con_la_acuicultura.html
	11/10/2022	Gran Canaria presenta AquaWind, proyecto pionero que vincula energía	Canarias Noticias	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://canariasnoticias.es/2022/10/11/gran-canaria-presenta-aquawind-proyecto-

		eólica y acuicultura				pionero-que-vincula-energia-eolica-y-acuicultura
11/10/2022	AquaWind busca integrar la eólica marina offshore con la acuicultura	INFOPUERTOS	ONLINE PRESS	National		https://infopuertos.com/aquawind-busca-integrar-la-eolica-marina-offshore-con-la-acuicultura/
12/10/2022	Ingenium o cómo posicionar en el sector de los parques eólicos marinos a una región sin acceso al mar	El Español	ONLINE PRESS	National		https://www.elespanol.com/invertia/disruptores-innovadores/autonomias/castilla-la-mancha/20221012/ingenium-posicionar-sector-parques-eolicos-marinos-sin/709929214_0.html
12/10/2022	Gran Canaria presenta un proyecto pionero que vincula energía eólica y acuicultura	SIGLO XXI	ONLINE PRESS	National		https://www.diariosigloxi.com/texto-diario/mostrar/3923898/gran-canaria-presenta-proyecto-pionero-vincula-energia-eolica-acuicultura
13/10/2022	Canarias acoge pruebas pioneras que combinan energías eólicas offshore y piscicultura	MisPeces	ONLINE PRESS	National		https://www.mispecies.com/noticias/Canarias-acoge-pruebas-pioneras-que-combinan-energias-eolicas-offshore-y-piscicultura/#.Y1---3bP1D8
14/10/2022	Canarias lidera el proyecto pionero AquaWind para fusionar energía eólica y acuicultura	INFOPUERTOS	ONLINE PRESS	National		https://infopuertos.com/canarias-lidera-el-proyecto-pionero-aquawind-para-fusionar-energia-eolica-y-acuicultura/
14/10/2022	Cómo combinar la energía eólica con la acuicultura	EnergyHub	ONLINE PRESS	Regional		http://www.energyhub.es/texto-diario/mostrar/3927225/como-combinar-energia-eolica-acuicultura

26/10/2022	Canarias lidera el proyecto AquaWind para fusionar energía eólica y acuicultura	El Espejo Canario	RADIO	Regional	https://www.elespejocanario.es/secciones/canarias-lidera-el-proyecto-aquawind-para-fusionar-energia-eolica-y-acuicultura/
26/10/2022	Economía Azul	El Espejo Canario	RADIO	Regional	https://www.elespejocanario.es/secciones/canarias-lidera-el-proyecto-aquawind-para-fusionar-energia-eolica-y-acuicultura/
30/09/2022	Protótipo Multiuso Inovador Combina Energía Renovável Offshore e Acuicultura na Bacia do Atlântico	Revista da Marinha	MAGAZINE	National	Printed edition - no link
11/10/2022	Arranca el proyecto europeo AquaWind, que une la energía eólica offshore con la acuicultura	OESA	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://www.observatorio-acuicultura.es/comunicacion/actualidad/arranca-el-proyecto-europeo-aquawind-que-une-la-energia-eolica-offshore-con
9/11/2022	Canarias lidera el proyecto AquaWind para fusionar energía eólica y acuicultura	BOLETÍN HONTZA	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://plocan.hontza.es/sbes/boletin_report/18/my_web/897
28/11/2022	Magnífica acogida del proyecto AquaWind en el Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura de Cádiz	INFOPUERTOS	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://infopuertos.com/magnifica-acogida-del-proyecto-aquawind-en-el-congreso-nacional-de-acuicultura-de-cadiz/
15/10/2022	La convivencia con la pesca centra el debate en las Jornadas de Eólica Marina	La Provincia	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://www.laprovincia.es/las-palmas/2022/10/15/convivencia-pesca-centra-debate-jornadas-77268407.html
15/10/2022	Encuentro de la eólica marina con el sector pesquero en	INFOPUERTOS	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://infopuertos.com/encuentro-de-la-eolica-

	Canarias					marina-con-el-sector-pesquero-en-canarias/
19/10/2022	Telde, centro de pruebas para el proyecto europeo AquaWind	TELDEACTUALIDAD	ONLINE PRESS	Regional		https://teldeactualidad.com/art/131815/medioambiente
20/10/2022	La eólica marina busca hacer las paces con la pesca	EnergyHub	ONLINE PRESS	Regional		http://www.energyhub.es/texto-diario/mostrar/3935742/eolica-marina-busca-hacer-paces-pesca
27/10/2022	La eólica marina offshore y el sector pesquero apuestan por la convivencia	INFOPUERTOS	ONLINE PRESS	National		https://infopuertos.com/la-eolica-marina-offshore-y-el-sector-pesquero-apuestan-por-la-convivencia/
27/10/2022	El CMC defiende una eólica marina en convivencia con la biodiversidad	Diario del Puerto	ONLINE PRESS	Regional		https://www.diariodelpuerto.com/maritimo/el-cmc-defiende-una-eolica-marina-en-convivencia-con-la-biodiversidad-ML12808307
25/11/2022	DEBATES DE INGENIERÍA DE LA ENERGÍA. COMBINAR ENERGÍA EÓLICA CON PISCIFACTORÍAS	Inmoley	ONLINE PRESS	National		https://www.inmoley.com/NOTICIAS/2212345/2022-1-inmobiliario-urbanismo-vivienda/011-22-inmobiliario-25-21.html
25/11/2022	AquaWind project makes a splash at Cádiz National Aquaculture Congress	The Fish Site	ONLINE PRESS	International		https://thefishsite.com/articles/aquawind-project-makes-a-splash-at-c%3%A1diz-national-aquaculture-congress
25/11/2022	AquaWind: energías renovables, seguridad alimentaria a través de la acuicultura y crecimiento azul	IPAC Acuicultura	ONLINE PRESS	National		http://www.ipacuicultura.com/noticias/en_portada/82525/aquawind-en-energias-renovables-seguridad-alimentaria-a-traves-de-la-acuicultura-y-crecimiento-azul.html
25/11/2022	AquaWind surprises at the Cádiz National	AquaHoy	ONLINE PRESS	National		https://aquahoy.com/aquawind-surprises-at-the-

	Aquaculture Congress				cadiz-national-aquaculture-congress/
25/11/2022	AquaWind sorprende en el Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura de Cádiz	Radio Faro del Noroeste	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://www.radiofarodelnoroeste.es/secciones/nacional/item/11972-aquawind-sorprende-en-el-congreso-nacional-de-acuicultura-de-cadiz
5/06/2023	European projects AquaWind and FLORA explore synergies in a joint event in Gran Canaria	AquaHoy	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://aquahoy.com/proyectos-europeos-aquawind-flora-exploran-sinergias-evento-conjunto-gran-canaria/
5/06/2023	Los proyectos europeos AquaWind y FLORA exploran sinergias	IPACacuicultura	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://www.ipacuicultura.com/noticia.php?id=67589
5/06/2023	Los proyectos europeos AquaWind y FLORA que se ensayarán en PLOCAN establecen las bases para futuras colaboraciones	INFOPUERTOS	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://infopuertos.com/los-proyectos-europeos-aquawind-y-flora-que-se-ensayaran-en-plocan-establecen-las-bases-para-futuras-colaboraciones/
7/06/2023	Plocan acoge el ensayo de los proyectos europeos AquaWind y Flora	ivoox	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://www.ivoox.com/plocan-acoge-ensayo-proyectos-europeos-audios-mp3_rf_109919440_1.html
07/06/2023	Plocan acoge el ensayo de los proyectos europeos AquaWind y Flora	El Espejo Canario	RADIO	Regional	https://www.elespejocanario.es/secciones/plocan-acoge-el-ensayo-de-los-proyectos-europeos-aquawind-y-flora/
08/06/2023	La Plocan acoge el ensayo de los proyectos europeos AquaWind y Flora	Energy hub	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	http://www.energyhub.es/texto-diario/mostrar/4326033/plocan-acoge-ensayo-proyectos-europeos-aquawind-flora

	09/06/2023	Offshore aquaculture/renewables projects explore synergies	The Fish Site	ONLINE PRESS	International	https://thefishsite.com/articles/offshore-aquaculture-renewables-projects-explore-synergies
	25/06/2023	El banco de ensayos pone a prueba los prototipos de AquaWind y Flora	TELDEACTUALIDAD	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://teldeactualidad.com/art/153702/el-banco-de-ensayos-pone-a-prueba-los-prototipos-de-aquawind-y-flora
	7/08/2023	La plataforma flotante del proyecto AquaWind unifica aerogeneradores e instalaciones de acuicultura	SMARTGRIDSINFO	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://www.smartgridsinfo.es/2023/08/07/plataforma-flotante-proyecto-aquawind-unifica-aerogeneradores-instalaciones-acuicultura
Year 2 (M13 – M24)	21/09/2023	Naturgy presenta el proyecto eólico marino Fowca en Gran Canaria	ENERGÍAS RENOVABLES	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://www.energias-renovables.com/eolica/el-congreso-navalia-meeting-pone-el-foco-20230921
	06/11/2023	Encuesta previa a la prueba del prototipo del proyecto AquaWind sobre energía marina y acuicultura	SMARTGRIDSINFO	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://www.smartgridsinfo.es/2023/11/06/encuesta-previa-prueba-prototipo-proyecto-aquawind-sobre-energia-marina-acuicultura
	08/02/2024	Gran Canaria impulsa la revolución en acuicultura offshore con un innovador prototipo de jaula	El Sur digital	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://elsurdigitalgc.es/art/13942/gran-canaria-impulsa-la-revolucion-en-acuicultura-offshore-con-un-innovador-prototipo-de-jaula
	08/02/2024	La revolución en la acuicultura offshore llega a Taliarte con una jaula innovadora	CANARIAS 7	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://www.canarias7.es/canarias/gran-canaria/telde/revolucion-acuicultura-offshore-llega-taliarte-jaula-innovadora-20240208172234-nt.html

08/02/2024	Gran Canaria impulsa la revolución en acuicultura offshore con un innovador prototipo de jaula	Digital Faro Canarias	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://www.digitalfarocanarias.com/index.php/2024/02/08/gran-canaria-impulsa-la-revolucion-en-acuicultura-offshore-con-un-innovador-prototipo-de-jaula/
09/02/2024	El Cabildo de Gran Canaria y AquaWind contribuyen al impulso de la acuicultura offshore con un innovador prototipo de jaula	IPACacuicultura	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://www.ipacuicultura.com/noticia-69222-seccion-Proyectos
09/02/2024	Gran Canaria impulsa la acuicultura offshore con un innovador prototipo de jaula	Puertos Canarias	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://puertocanarias.com/es/ciencia
10/02/2024	AquaWind diseña un innovador prototipo de jaula para la acuicultura offshore	INFOPUERTOS	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://infopuertos.com/aquawind-disena-un-innovador-prototipo-de-jaula-para-la-acuicultura-offshore/
13/03/2024	Cuenta atrás para la botadura de la primera plataforma multiuso de eólica flotante	ESPIRAL 21	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://espiral21.com/cuenta-atras-para-la-botadura-de-la-primer-plataforma-multiuso-de-eolica-flotante/
13/03/2024	La primera plataforma multiuso de eólica flotante y acuicultura ya está lista para su botadura	La Provincia	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://www.laprovincia.es/canarias/2024/03/13/primera-plataforma-multiuso-eolica-flotante-99429019.html
13/03/2024	Acto informativo en Astican con motivo de la visita del Consorcio de AquaWind al prototipo W2Power	Canarias 7	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://www.canarias7.es/canarias/gran-canaria/las-palmas-de-gran-canaria/acto-informativo-astican-motivo-visita-consorcio-

					aquawind-20240313154745-vi.html
13/03/2024	Prueban en Gran Canaria la primera plataforma flotante de eólica y acuicultura de España	EFE	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://efe.com/canarias/2024-03-13/prueban-en-gran-canaria-la-primera-plataforma-flotante-de-eolica-y-acuicultura-de-espana/
14/03/2024	Progress continues at Atlantic's first offshore wind and aquaculture platform	The fish site	ONLINE PRESS	International	https://thefishsite.com/articles/progress-continues-at-atlantics-first-offshore-wind-and-aquaculture-platform
14/03/2024	La plataforma multiuso de eólica flotante y acuicultura del proyecto AquaWind lista para comenzar los ensayos en condiciones reales	IPACacuicultura	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://www.ipacuicultura.com/noticia-69472-seccion-Proyectos
20/03/2024	La plataforma multiuso de eólica flotante y acuicultura del proyecto AquaWind lista para comenzar los ensayos en condiciones reales	IPACacuicultura	NEWSLETTER	National	https://www.ipacuicultura.com/noticia-69472-seccion-Proyectos
20/03/2024	Estudiantes europeos de carreras tecnológicas conocen de primera mano el proyecto AquaWind	IPACacuicultura	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://www.ipacuicultura.com/noticia-69516-seccion-General
21/03/2024	Estudiantes de carreras tecnológicas conocen de primera mano el proyecto AquaWind coordinado por ACISI	Radio Faro del Norte	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://www.radiofarodelnoroeste.es/secciones/internacional/item/24587-estudiantes-de-carreras-tecnologicas-conocen-de-primera-mano-el-proyecto-aquawind-coordinado-por-aciisi

21/05/2024	Los socios de AquaWind se capacitan en seguridad y salud ante el lanzamiento en otoño del piloto de la plataforma multipropósito	IPACacuicultura	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://www.ipacuicultura.com/noticia-69933-seccion-Laboral-y-Formaci%C3%B3n
15/06/2024	El auditorio Alfredo Kraus acoge XIX Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura del 17 al 19 de junio	El Periódico de Canarias	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://www.elperiodico.decanarias.es/el-auditorio-alfredo-kraus-acoge-el-xix-congreso-nacional-de-acuicultura-del-17-al-19-de-junio/#google_vignette
17/06/2024	Gran Canaria se convierte en la capital española de la acuicultura	La Provincia	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://www.laprovincia.es/sociedad/2024/06/17/gran-canaria-convierte-capital-espanola-103914092.html
17/06/2024	El Auditorio Alfredo Kraus acoge desde hoy y hasta el miércoles, 19 de junio, el XIX Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura	IPACacuicultura	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://www.ipacuicultura.com/noticia-70123-seccion-General
18/06/2024	Mas de 200 investigadores se reúnen en la cumbre nacional de la acuicultura española en Gran Canaria	Tribuna de Canarias	ONLINE PRESS	Regional	https://tribunadecanarias.es/mas-de-200-investigadores-se-reunen-en-la-cumbre-nacional-de-la-acuicultura-espanola-en-gran-canaria/
21/06/2024	ESPAÑA: El XIX Congreso Nacional de Acuicultura presenta THINKINAZUL	Mundo Acuicola	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://www.mundoacuicola.cl/new/espana-el-xix-congreso-nacional-de-acuicultura-presenta-thinkinazul/
21/06/2024	El XIX CNA presenta un proyecto impulsado en Fuerteventura que multiplicará por cinco la producción	EBF NOTICIAS	ONLINE PRESS	National	https://www.elblogoferoz.com/2024/06/18/las-palmas-el-xix-cna-presenta-un-proyecto-impulsado-en-

		anual de langostino blanco en España				fuerteventura-que-multiplicara-por-cinco-la-produccion-anual-de-langostino-blanco-en-espana/
05/07/2024	Gender Equality practices in different sectors	EU ATHENA Newsletter	NEWSLETTER	International		https://www.athenaequality.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/ATHENA-Newsletter-issue-05_vf.pdf
12/07/2024	I+D para un futuro verde con fondo azul	Ciencia Canaria	ONLINE PRESS	REGIONAL		https://www.cienciacanaria.es/secciones/a-fondo/1310-i-d-para-un-futuro-verde-con-fondo-azul
09/08/2023	Innovación verde y azul en Canarias con ACISI y Aquawind	Noticia 8 islas canarias	ONLINE PRESS	REGIONAL		https://noticias8islas.com/innovacion-verde-azul-canarias-aciisi-aquawind/

In this context, WP leader has been compiling press interviews according to GA guidelines and the D&C Plan:

- Quotes for Strategic Communications: these quotes are used in strategic communications, web publications and social media, and are planned to be broadcast on radio and/or podcasts.
- Videos: Short video segments are created that can be posted on social media and broadcast on television and other media.
- Radio interviews: These interviews are done mainly on national and regional radio stations.

CE has collected testimonies from partners and other stakeholders during the first two years of the project, which have been used for strategic communications including the development of press releases and the promotional videos. In collaboration with partner CMC - Cluster Marítimo de Canarias, three local radio interviews focused on AquaWind have been achieved.

2.6 Promotional videos

As per GA, three promotional videos shall be produced by AquaWind as follows:

- A first **animation video** at the beginning of the project to inform about the objectives and vision of it.
- A **storytelling video** involving staff from the project and other stakeholders involved in the project activities.
- A **demonstration video** of the technological and operational aspects of the AquaWind solution.

The videos are to be produced in English with subtitles in the three languages of the Consortium (Spanish, Portuguese, French). These videos shall be uploaded to AquaWind's YouTube and distributed across partners' websites and other channels.

The first video was produced and released at M12 (see D7.2 Videos Ver. 1), with the aim of presenting the overall scope of AquaWind, its objectives, and main activities and results expected from this funding experience.

The video is available on AquaWind Youtube channel and website's homepage. On YouTube channel, videos with subtitles in the project languages are also provided.

The production process of the first video involved CE crafting the script and collaborating with partners on its development. Following pre-production, graphic elements were designed, leading to the creation of a captivating video. More information is provided in D7.2.

The second video has been just released at M24 (see D7.3 Ver. 2), compiling the experiences and comments of all project partners. This video is designed to provide a comprehensive and personal view of how each partner contributes to the success of the project, highlighting project partners experiences and the impact of their specific roles.

Each partner shares their perspective on the project in the video, creating an enriching story that demonstrates the teamwork and commitment of all participants. These interviews and stories not only highlight the unique contributions of each partner, but also provide a comprehensive view of the teamwork and accomplishments that have been achieved thus far.

The storytelling video has just been released and is available on the project's YouTube channel and can be accessed at any time to learn more about the stories behind the project. In addition, the video will be soon accessible also on the AquaWind website, along with other resources and updates related to the project.

A social media campaign will be launched from September 2024, aiming to promote the video and increase its visibility in the future. To reach a wider audience, this campaign

will include planned posts on various social media platforms. In addition, all partners will be encouraged to share the video on their official channels to increase its reach and encourage wider dissemination of the content. The goal of this initiative is to improve project communication by highlighting the achievements and collaboration between partners, as well as to encourage greater engagement and recognition within the community. More information is provided in D7.2 and D7.3.

2.7 Events

Attendance to events

AquaWind consortium members have been actively involved in a variety of events over the past two years. The contribution of the scientific community, political leaders, industry stakeholders and the general public at regional, national and European level has been crucial to give visibility and recognition to the project.

Moreover, it has enabled the establishment of connections and potential synergies including with other EU funded projects.

The table below show the attended events by the consortium during the first two years of the project where AquaWind has been promoted.

Table 9. Attended events by AquaWind Consortium

	Partner	Type of event	Target group	Name	Location	Date
Year 1 (M1-12)	EnerOcean, WavEC	Conference participation	Industry; Scientific Community	International Ocean Conference on Ocean Energy (ICOE)	San Sebastián, Spain	18/10/2022 - 20/10/2022
	GOBCAN-ACIISI, ULPGC, CE	Conference participation	Industry; Scientific Community	Spanish National aquaculture Congress	Cádiz, Spain	21/11/2022 - 24/11/2022
	EnerOcean	Conference participation	Industry; Scientific Community	InnovAzul - II Encuentro Internacional de Conocimiento y Economía Azul	Cádiz, Spain	29/11/2022-30/11/2022
	CMC	Conference participation	Policy makers	EMFAF 2022 Info Day	Brussels, Belgium	24/11/2022

	CE	Exhibition	Policy Makers; Others	EU Missions - Restore our ocean and waters	Brussels, Belgium	17/02/2023
	All partners	Conference participation	Investors; Industry	AquaFuture Spain	Santiago De Compostela, Spain	28/03/2024-30/03/2023
	CMC, CE, PLOCAN	Exhibition	Quadruple helix	FIMAR 2023 - Feria Internacional del Mar 2023	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain	16/06/2024-18/06/2023
Year 2 (M13-24)	GOBCAN-ACIISI; CMC, CE, PLOCAN	Conference participation	Quadruple helix	Navalia 2023	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain	22/09/2023
	GOBCAN-ACIISI; CMC, EnerOcean	Conference participation	Industry, Investors, Scientific Community	OffShore Wind Congress	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain	7/11/2024 - 8/11/2023
	GOBCAN-ACIISI, ULPGC, CMC, CE	Conference participation	Quadruple helix	World Aquaculture Day Professional Sessions	Taliarte, Gran Canaria, Spain	30/11/2023
	CE	Poster participation	Quadruple helix	European Ocean Days	-	6/03/2024
	WavEC	Conference participation	Industry, Scientific Community, Investors	Lisbon Energy Summit	Lisbon, Portugal	2/06/2024-4/06/2024
	CMC, ENEROCEANS, WavEC	Conference participation	Industry, Scientific Community, Investors	WindEurope 2024	Bilbao, Spain	20/03/2024 – 22/03/2024
	CMC, CE	Exhibition	Quadruple helix	FIMAR 2024	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain	7/06/2024 - 9/06/2024
	CE	Participation in activities organised	EU project and	ATHENA workshop on gender equality	Rome, Italy	18/06/2024

		jointly with other EU projects	Scientific Community	and blue economy		
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Organisation of events

Effective communication and engagement with the scientific community and the general public is essential for the AquaWind project. AquaWind partners have organised several events during the two years of the project described below. These events were aimed at fostering interaction, dissemination of information about the project and active participation of a wide range of stakeholders.

Table 10. Organised events by AquaWind Consortium

	Organising partner	Type of event	WP	Target group	Name of the event	Date	Location
Year 1 (M1-12)	CMC organiser (with support of GOBCAN-ACIISI and CE)	Conference	WP1, WP7	Fisheries communities	Jornada de Energía Eólica Marina en Canarias. Proyección y retos (EN: Conference on Offshore Wind Energy in the Canary Islands. Challenges and opportunities)	25/10/2022	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain
	CMC and CE organisers. Participation of all partners	Workshop	WP7	Sister project	AQUAWIND-FLORA Joint Event (Sister project)	01/06/2023	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain
Year 2 (M13-24)	GOBCAN-ACIISI	Conference	WP1, WP7	Policy Makers /Quadruple helix	Smart Specialisation Strategy (RIS3) in the Canary Islands: Blue Economy Informative Day	13/12/2023	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain
	GOBCAN-ACIISI	Conference	WP1, WP7	Policy Makers/ Quadruple helix	Smart Specialisation Strategy (RIS3) in the Canary Islands: Technological Breakfast	31/01/2024	Fuerteventura, Spain

GOBCAN-ACIISI, CE	Training session	WP7	Students	AquaWind and BEST (Board of European Students of Technology) event	19/03/2024	Taliarte, Gran Canaria, Spain
CMC, GOBCAN-ACIISI	Conference	WP1, WP7	Quadruple helix, Civil Society	El Hierro, an island with projection in R&D&I in the extended RIS3	14/06/2024	El Hierro, Spain
GOBCAN-ACIISI, ULPGC, CE, PLOCAN, CMC	Conference	WP1, WP7	Quadruple helix, Civil Society	XIX National Aquaculture Congress 2024	17/06/2024-20/06/2024	Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain
CE, PLOCAN	Webinar	WP7	Industry, Investors, Scientific Community	Webinar - FLORA and AquaWind (Sister Project)	20/06/2024	Online
CMC, GOBCAN-ACIISI	Conference	WP1, WP7	Quadruple helix, Civil society	La Gomera, an island with projection in R&D&I in the extended RIS3	24/07/2024	San Sebastián de La Gomera, Spain
CMC, GOBCAN -ACIISI	Conference	WP1, WP7	Quadruple helix, Civil society	La Palma, an island with projection in R&D&I in the extended RIS3	01/08/2024	Santa Cruz de La Palma, Spain

The events have been organised mainly in the framework of Work Packages 1 and 7. The main objective of these events is to make the general public as well as the scientific community aware of the potential, perspectives and challenges of offshore wind energy in the Canary Islands. They also provide an opportunity to present the AquaWind project

and to distribute the Work Package 1 survey, thus allowing for the collection of useful information and feedback from stakeholders.

These events aimed to establish a cooperative and inclusive approach to offshore wind energy development in the area. In certain cases, they also sought to promote the participation of local fishing communities, ensuring that their views and concerns are heard during the offshore energy development process.

2.8 Synergies with other Work Packages

WP7 works in close **synergy** with **WP1, WP5, and WP6**. WP1 oversees stakeholder planning (task 1.3) and stakeholder engagement activities (task 1.4), while WP5 fosters and maximises the exploitation opportunities of the AquaWind multi-use solution. WP6 includes a task (6.7) regarding gender auditing and guidelines through which the project shall also promote actions to raise awareness about gender and diversity principles in the blue economy sector.

When it comes to **WP1**, at the project start, a mapping of stakeholders of the quadruple helix (task 1.3) has been carried out with the aim of ensuring a wide representation of target groups in the project. The deliverable “D1.3 Stakeholder Engagement Plan”, submitted at M6 (February 2023), has been a key reference guide for the planning and implementation of D&C actions under WP7.

During the second year of the project, a series of key messages were created to promote a technical survey seeking feedback from stakeholders. These key messages have been disseminated through social networks, websites and media to reach the entire target audience.

Some of these key messages are as follows:

- We want to hear from you!
- Have your say!
- We value your feedback!
- Give us your opinion!
- We need your brilliance!
- Your opinion matter!

WP7 designed a series of engaging illustrations based on these key phrases that reflect the corporate identity of the project. These illustrations have been carefully designed to capture the attention of our stakeholders and convey key messages effectively.

They have been adapted for use in a variety of digital formats, such as web banners and social media posts, allowing us to maximise the reach and impact of our communications campaign, as well as a poster with a QR that takes you to the survey link which has been promoted at some events. In addition, each illustration is aligned with the project’s branding strategy to ensure visual consistency and increase brand recognition across all platforms.

Figure 23. Banner web for survey

Table 11. Series of social media posts for the promotion of the survey

Figure 24. Poster with QR that takes you to the link’s survey

Regarding collaboration with WP5 activities, several events and dissemination activities, including the promotion of the WP1 survey, have served to gather feedback from the quadruple helix stakeholders about the potential exploitation of the AquaWind innovation, especially referring to the business case of the prototype and the policy recommendations which are to be drafted in task 5.9 'Recommendations for policy makers. For instance, the organisation of the FLORA-AquaWind webinar has been a key activity to retrieve inputs for WP5 tasks.

Finally, WP6 (task 6.7) has benefitted from WP7 activities, considering that synergies have been established with two other EU-funded projects (ATHENA and WINBLUE) in the field of gender and diversity promotion. More information is provided in the following section.

2.9 Synergies with other projects/initiatives

EMFAF FLORA project

AquaWind has successfully established a collaboration channel with the **sister project FLORA** (<https://wedgeglobal.com/projects/>). The FLORA technology, developed by Wedge Global, aims to optimise and validate a multisensory ocean station prototype that generates energy to support its oceanographic data services. Similar to AquaWind's W2Power prototype, the FLORA system undergoes real-sea testing at the PLOCAN test site for several months, aligning with the objectives of the Atlantic Maritime Strategy to promote marine renewable energies and sustainable growth of the blue economy in the Atlantic region.

The FLORA project is particularly interesting since like AquaWind it will perform its testing activities in the Atlantic Ocean and particularly in the same test site area at PLOCAN, Gran Canaria. This is interesting as synergies for data collection and sharing can be evaluated.

To forge this mutual collaboration, a first hybrid **joint event** was organised by AquaWind at the premises of CMC on **1st June 2023** and attended by both project consortium members. An additional online technical meeting was held later on, during 2023, to continue discussions on the potential collaborations.

Figure 25. AquaWind – FLORA consortium

Contacts and information exchanges has continued during 2024. This led to the joint organization of a successful webinar entitled ‘Demonstration of a Multipurpose Sea Platform’, held on 20th June 2024.

The event aimed to present the strategy, pillars and calls of the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF). Furthermore, the activities of the two EU projects FLORA and AquaWind were presented. On one side, the market potential of FLORA - a self-sustained, multi-sensor oceanic station for offshore environmental monitoring, was analysed. On the other side, AquaWind activities in relation to legal permits for multi-use projects and related health & safety operations were presented and discussed with the audience. Finally, a recent commercial client of the FLORA station - Ecowende – presented their project of sustainable offshore wind farm under development in the Netherlands, showcasing an example of potential commercial application of multi-use technologies.

Figure 26. AquaWind – FLORA webinar

ATHENA Project

On June 18, 2024 AquaWind was presented in Rome at the Workshop of the [ATHENA project](#). ATHENA is a H2020 funded project that aims at implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential across different research organisations in Europe. In the workshop, AquaWind presented their approach and activities related to gender and diversity principles and also gathered feedback from ATHENA's experts and stakeholders for its 6.7 gender auditing task.

Figure 27. AquaWind – ATHENA's Workshop

WINBLUE Project

On June 7 and 19, 2024 the EMFAF [WINBLUE project](#) held two workshops with a specific focus on the offshore renewable energy sector, with the objective of identifying best practices, barriers, and possible solutions for the implementation of gender equality plans in the blue economy. Hosted in Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, these events brought together quadruple helix representatives to reflect on gender and diversity challenges and opportunities in the field of offshore energy. AquaWind participated in these workshops sharing views and inputs for the development of a template of Gender Equality Plan, which could be used in future by companies and other stakeholders from the sector.

Figure 28. - Workshop on Gender Equality in the Blue Economy: Application of gender equality plan models in the offshore renewable energy sector

2.10 Open-access

AquaWind is dedicated to upholding the principles and practices of Open Science and Open Access throughout the entire duration of the project, from its initiation to its completion. This commitment entails depositing public data generated by AquaWind into reputable open-access repositories, in accordance with the guidelines set forth by EMFAF as well as by the Horizon Europe (HE) programme on open access and utilising open licenses.

Placed on AquaWind's website, a “Results” section guarantees that all approved public deliverables by the EU are published and accessible for stakeholders throughout the project's lifespan. This section serves as a valuable resource for stakeholders to stay updated on the progress, findings, and outcomes of the AquaWind project. The section also includes produced dissemination material ready to be downloaded, as well as gives promotion to the developed project videos.

In addition, the project is making use of Zenodo platform to share its findings, data and other outputs. Zenodo is a digital repository that offers researchers, scientists, and scholars a platform to openly share and preserve their research outputs, including datasets, software, images, videos, deliverables, and other publications. Operated by CERN and supported by funding from the European Commission, Zenodo guarantees its long-term sustainability and preservation.

A [Zenodo Community for AquaWind](#) has been created and approved public deliverables have been uploaded to the platform. This community is used for the dissemination of other open-access and non-confidential data and publications that will be produced by the consortium in the next two years of the project. CE, the WP7 Leader, oversees keeping the platform updated.

3. Monitoring and evaluation of dissemination activities

Within the framework of WP7, task 7.5 deals with the monitoring and evaluation of D&C activities. These are being monitored to ensure they are properly implemented and support the maximisation of the project's expected impacts. Monitoring of the activities allows to assess if the actions planned are carried out properly and on time and to measure their effectiveness. Based on monitoring results, the project D&C Plan might be thus reformulated to improve the communication and dissemination outreach.

To monitor the project, partners are periodically requested to provide information on the activities carried out (for instance organisation of events, publications of news/press releases, etc., presentations at conferences) while CE is in charge of monitoring and reporting on the use of the website, social media, and on the events whose organisation is under CE's responsibility. Based on the reports submitted from the partners, CE can formulate recommendations for the future dissemination and communication activities.

A continuous monitoring of the dissemination activities made by project partners is carried out within WP7 tasks. An internal file shared among partners keeps records of the press releases, articles, and events, gathering the information based on:

- The partner who carried out the activity.
- The date which the activity took place in.
- Activity outreach.
- Publication source.
- URL link to the activity results or proof.
- Targeted audience.
- In case of an event, the type of event, location, and general information.

Indicators' monitoring

In conjunction with the monitoring, an evaluation of the effectiveness of the activities will be performed periodically mainly using a set of target indicators of success set in the Grant Agreement and reported in the table below. The continuous monitoring will allow CE to assess the evolution and impacts of the dissemination and communication activities and evaluate any corrections or preventive measures to increase the reach-out of WP7 activities.

Table 12. Monitoring and evaluation indicators' progress at M24

Indicator	Target as per GA	Indicator progress at M12	Indicator progress at M24	Level of completion*
Participation in national/EU events	6	7	15	250%
Organisation of international conference	1 (with 80 attendants)	0	0	0% (to be organised at project end)
Production of newsletter	6	1	3	50%
Newsletter subscribers	148	155	243	164%
N° of interviews	9 (3/year)	3	3	66%
N° of press releases	9	36	62	688%
Website visits per month	227	~152	247	108%
N° of peer reviewed publications	3	0	0	0%
Total followers (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube)	1000	926	1849	184%
N° of videos produced	3	1	2	66%
N° of webinars/events	4 (2 for civil society organisations; 2 for policy makers)	1 (face-to-face event for civil society & fishery communities)	1 for fisheries communities; 5 for quadruple helix stakeholders (policy makers, academia, industry, society); 2 with sister project (FLORA); 1 scientific community; 1 university students	250%

- Not started yet
- Ongoing / on track
- Already achieved or even overpassed

Overall, the monitoring of the indicators set out in the GA indicates progress in the dissemination and communication actions for AquaWind, and the European and local communities have responded positively. As shown in the table above, several indicators

are in progress due to the fact that there is still one year left to complete the project. The project has not only reached its targets, but also exceeded them on some indicators, such as attendance at events, number of press releases and number of supporters. This demonstrates both the consortium's efforts and the high level of interest in the project so far. However, peer-reviewed publications have not yet started.

Conclusions

This report provided a summary of the dissemination and communication (D&C) activities carried out during the first 24 months of the AquaWind project. The WP7 leader, together with all project partners, has worked on the development and launch of communication and dissemination tools, as well as the implementation of activities associated with them, in accordance with the strategy outlined in the AquaWind Dissemination and Communication Plan (D7.1).

Each communication and dissemination initiative has been created to achieve a specific objective and targets specific project stakeholders. A variety of communication tools, including brochures, roll-ups and customised templates, have been used to present a consistent message and a coherent visual identity to the target audience.

Stakeholders have been kept informed of project progress through the project website, events, social media channels and newsletters. Press releases have also contributed to the media coverage and visibility of AquaWind.

In addition, partnerships and collaborations with related initiatives and projects have been grown to promote AquaWind and increase stakeholder engagement.

Last but not least, dissemination and communication activities are progressing according to plan, and the final phase of WP7 activities will focus on optimising the results achieved so far. The promotion of more technical activities related to the soon-to-be-completed AquaWind prototype will be part of this approach.

AQUAWIND

Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin

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